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KEY WORDS

THE ROLE OF CREATIVE IDEAS IN PROMOTING PEDAGOGICAL EFFECTIVENESS

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ABSTRACT

Creativity is one of the most valued learning skills in the 21st century. It is important to develop creativity in order to achieve an effective and high level of education. As different approaches to its study, creativity has been defined as a result, as a process, as a construction arising from the influence of context and experience, and as a personal feature of human nature. The purpose of this contribution is to explain the study of creativity in order to gain an understanding of such a construction based on the approaches mentioned above. In addition, the main focus is on the development and application of creative strategies in the teaching and learning process, from the impact, to the development of creativity from an educational approach. A brief description of the most important or relevant strategies found in the literature emphasizes the inclusion of these strategies in the problem-solving process.

Introduction

Creativity is one of the most appreciated learning skills current the XXI century. Creativity is conceived as a higher-order thinking skill based on complex and postformal thought concerned with the creation of new and valuable ideas. Higher-order thinking skills are those involved in proficient and strategic thought, and these skills comprise critical, creative and metacognitive thinking, also known as deep learning. In addition, the development of creativity is today considered essential in order to achieve an effective and a high-level learning.

Despite the observed need for the development of creativity in the curriculum, there is a general tendency to reproduce teaching and learning models and a constraint on teacher's search for procedures to teach creativity, which involves little creativity development in students, with a predominance of reproductive learning. The article presents four years of follow-up research that has shown that it is possible to increase creativity in all students using a variety of teaching methods and strategies. Strategies encourage creativity, including engaging students in activities they enjoy and find unique, encouraging students to present their ideas orally and discuss with others,

and giving students the opportunity to develop evidence-based reasoning. Students should be encouraged to value empirical evidence and relevant knowledge and ideas, identify and address barriers, explore the lives and contributions of creative individuals throughout history, collaborate with others, take intellectual risks, and learn from mistakes to develop cognitive abilities. Self-efficacy. The research presented here has shown that teaching critical analysis of art encourages students to establish emotional connections with the environment, to develop a more holistic understanding of works of art and the creative processes behind them. Encourages creativity in students by stimulating creative thinking skills and directions that help develop intellectual abilities. This paper presents research conducted at the National Gallery of Victoria in Melbourne into methods that may facilitate students' greater engagement, learning, and creativity by exposing them to art installations, paintings, and modern and traditional art forms, and encouraging them to respond creatively to the stories behind the artworks. Vygotsky proposed that "creativity arises from any human activity that produces something new". Within his constructivist theory, the analysis of art has the potential to facilitate the development of higher cognitive abilities and provides an opportunity for collaborative learning when undertaken in group contexts. Further proposed that many advances gained through human creativity and productivity have relied on collective creativity, in which small individual contributions combine to produce a greater outcome than individuals could have produced alone. Creativity of this kind should be encouraged among contemporary engineering and science

students to support the problem-solving and critical thinking required to produce practical and theoretical solutions for complex modern problems. Research indicates that modern workplaces demand critical thinking and creativity from employees, and these qualities are associated with higher productivity for employers and better work-life balance for employees. Employees who can process large amounts of disparate information and apply critical thinking to problem-solve, including scientists and engineers, represent a competitive advantage for businesses. In addition, these abilities are likely to extend the lifespans of businesses and increase their organisational capacity to recruit and retain more highly-skilled employees. Critically, creative thinking is teachable, and the work of learning to think creatively is carried forward to be applied by learners across their later work. That is, the work of learning creativity leads to the development of learners' creative abilities, which are then applied in the workplace. There is a consensus among scientists and scientist educators that scientific knowledge is the product of creative thinking. Thus, the demand for greater creativity in education is due not only to its recognised pedagogical effectiveness but also to the demands of the global economy for flexibility and adaptation to deliver innovation and competitiveness. However, empirical evidence has shown that there is a lack of appreciation of the importance of creative thinking among undergraduate engineering and science students. Enhancing classroom creativity and developing technology skills is the future of education and can become a powerful tool for overcoming class inequalities. This article examines a systematic scale review

of the literature focusing on the state of digital technology incorporated into social creativity and science education. For this purpose, 23 empirical studies were selected from several databases - all in English and reviewed blindly - to address the interrelationships of the main topics included in the following three research questions: What digital technology roles support collaboration and creative processes in science education? What forms and technological features of technology support and organize the above-mentioned creative processes? and what pedagogical principles guide the development of social creativity through the use of technology in science education and involve all students? The results show that technology can play a variety of roles in the development of social creativity: as a tutoring tool that nurtures some basic scientific creative processes. As a means of shaping students' creative thinking; and as a means of creating a conducive environment for the implementation of collective creative processes. In our project, these three roles were performed using a wide range of web 2.0 technologies web-based environments, digital platforms, mobile technologies, which involved all students in an active and rich user experience to create shared knowledge, and all students equipped. In a rapidly changing world, they have the necessary skills to turn them into active, Dynamic and resourceful citizens. There is a widespread notion that educational systems should empower learners with skills and competences to cope with a constantly changing landscape. Reference is often made to skills such as critical thinking, problem solving, collaborative skills, innovation, digital literacy, and adaptability. What is

negotiable is how best to achieve the development of those skills, in particular which teaching and learning approaches are suitable for facilitating or enabling complex skills development. In this paper, we build on our previous work of exploring new forms of pedagogy for an interactive world, as documented in our Innovating Pedagogy report series. We present a set of innovative pedagogical approaches that have the potential to guide teaching and transform learning. An integrated framework has been developed to select pedagogies for inclusion in this paper, consisting of the following five dimensions:

- * relevance to effective educational theories,
- * research evidence about the effectiveness of the proposed pedagogies,
- * relation to the development of twenty-first century skills,
- * innovative aspects of pedagogy,
- * level of adoption in educational practice.

The selected pedagogies, namely formative analytics, teachback, place-based learning, learning with drones, learning with robots, and citizen inquiry are either attached to specific technological developments, or they have emerged due to an advanced understanding of the science of learning. Each one is presented in terms of the five dimensions of the framework. "Creativity is as important in education as literacy and we should treat it with the same status".

Every child has some inborn potential of creativeness. Creativity plays a crucial role in the aspect of developing personality and provides a direction to analyze things diversely and uncommonly. Creativity does not just happen, it needs to be cultivated,

nurtured and needs a proper direction. Beginning of this cultivation process of creativity starts from the classroom and the teachers play a very important role in maintaining and process. There are lots of ways in which the teachers can play their part both inside and outside the classroom and being an international boarding school in Dehradun we have to incorporate new and innovative things for the students. We are living in the 21st century and technology is dominant everywhere in the education industry. Nowadays, there are various methods to include access to technological tools that helps to generate the creativity and innovation in the students. Our international boarding school maintains an ideal supply of all technological tools and devices to the students. Majorly active learning includes the addition of creative touch to already existing concepts, maps and study materials. It then becomes the responsibility of the teachers to initiate, cultivate and maintain creative thought through active learning methods. It can be done in the following way.

*Create interaction opportunity among students to initiate problem-solving attitude.

*Provide them with a lot of opportunities for hands-on fieldwork.

*Organize round-table discussion from time to time for the interesting topics.

*Allow students to create some of the questions for their upcoming exam.

It is true that teachers play an important role in developing students' creative abilities. It can be assumed that how teachers respond to students' ideas, views,

and suggestions throughout the lesson will affect students' subsequent actions and their tendency to come up with new ideas, views, and suggestions. A teacher's timely positive responses naturally encourage students' subsequent efforts, whereas the teacher's early and especially negative responses discourage students from further creative exploration. In short, teachers are able to demonstrate creative nurturing behaviors in daily communication with their students and are in a strategic position to develop students' creativity if they are in the habit. However, it is true that not all teachers have the capacity to build such capacity. They may or may not know the impact of their creativity-related behaviors on their students' behaviors. They should therefore be aware of their potential impact on students' creativity and teach them to demonstrate creative behaviors in the classroom. Creativity is the most difficult thinking skill to acquire, and also the most sought-after. We value it in our music, entertainment, technology, and other aspects of our existence. We appreciate and yearn for it because it enriches our understanding and can make life easier. What's important in any creative act is the process of self-expression. Creative experiences can help children express and cope with their feelings. Creativity also fosters mental growth in children by providing opportunities for trying out new ideas, and new ways of thinking and problem-solving. Often, our primary goals are directed at keeping children healthy and safe, teaching cognitive skills such as shape and color recognition, encouraging prosocial behavior, and introducing basic literacy and numeration skills. With all the time that needs to be devoted to these areas, there is less opportunity to think about the

importance of nurturing children's creative abilities. And yet, creative power increases a young child's desire to learn and supports intellectual development. Ask five different teachers to define "creativity" and you'll probably get five different answers. One definition of creativity focuses on the process of "divergent thinking," which involves:

- the breaking up of old ideas
- making new connections
- enlarging the limits of knowledge
- the onset of wonderful ideas

In conclusion, it can be argued that development involves the ability to increase complexity, and in general, human thinking is diverse, complex, and multifaceted, requiring the coordination of many cognitive processes. Therefore, we

emphasize the importance of developing high-level thinking skills, particularly those that have proven to be most effective in the teaching-learning process, critical, creative, and metacognitive thinking skills. Traditionally, education has focused more on developing critical, analytical or formal thinking skills, while creative thinking processes have been neglected. Therefore, this chapter is highlighted as an object of development and study of creative abilities. Creativity is a complex and multidimensional structure that makes it difficult to define clearly and consensually. However, it should be noted that the different approaches available in the study of creativity provide a complementary view of creativity and provide more insight for future research, which is creative and participatory in human thinking. Serves to explore processes and mechanisms as well as factors. Exposure to them.

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